

Ontological foundations

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The core of the PReM method is motivational goal modelling that has ontological foundations described in [3]. We now extend the ontological foundations of motivational goal modelling for the PReM method based on [2, 3, 1].

Ontological analysis divides entities into individuals and universals. *Individuals* are entities that exist at least in time, such as humans, machines, actions and events. An example of an entity that exists in time but not necessarily in space is a computer program. Each individual has a specific identity. *Universals* are patterns or features, which can be realized in a number of different individuals. Examples of universals are mathematical objects such as numbers and sets, modeling constructs such as goals and roles, and types such as types of agents, objects, and actions. Individuals can be distinguished from universals by the “causality criterion”, according to which an individual can cause another individual and instantiate one or more universals. Ontologically, two types of individuals are distinguished by their behaviour over time: endurants and events. Simply put, while endurants “exist in time”, events “happen in time”. *Endurant* is accordingly defined as an entity that maintains its identity over time. An endurant can be an agent, a non-agentive object, or moment. **Agent** is a kind of individual that can perform actions, perceive events, and reason. An agent can be a physical agent, such as a person or chatbot, or an institutional agent – organization. Agents perform roles. **Role** is a non-strict type, as agents belonging to it can change their type. *Moment* is an entity that represents some property of an individual. **Functional goal** is a situation intended by one or more agents. **Quality goal** is a moment that describes desired properties of the functional goal. *Action* is an intentional event that is performed with the purpose of achieving some goal. *Event* separates from each other two different situations, which are collective states of the entities of the problem domain under inspection respectively before and after it has occurred. **Process**, such as a *business process*, is a complex event consisting of two or more sequential or parallel events. Finally, **resource** is a non-agentive object that an agent performing some role needs for achieving its goals.

References

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